

EFFECTIVENESS OF REFORMS TO UPGRADE THE TRAINING OF PROSPECTIVE MIDDLE-LEVEL PERSONNEL LAWYERS

Rakhmatullayeva Kamola Amirkulovna

Head of the dormitory of the Legal

Technicum of Samarkand region

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Abstract. This article analyzes the role of middle-level legal personnel lawyers in building a fair society in our country and increasing the international reputation of our country, the current potential of legal personnel and the trends of increasing demand for them.

Keywords: law, personnel, lawyer, training.

Today, the analysis of the role of middle-level legal personnel in the establishment of a fair society in our country and the rise of the international reputation of our country, the current potential of legal personnel and the trends of increasing demand for them are analyzed. A lawyer is a person who practices law. The role of a lawyer varies greatly across different legal jurisdictions. A lawyer can be classified as an advocate, attorney, barrister, canon lawyer, civil law notary, counsel, solicitor, legal executive, or public servant — with each role having different functions and privileges. Working as a lawyer generally involves the practical application of abstract legal theories and knowledge to solve specific problems. Some lawyers also work primarily in advancing the interests of the law and legal profession. The educational prerequisites for becoming a lawyer vary greatly from country to country. In some countries, law is taught by a faculty of law, which is a department of a university's general undergraduate college. Law students in those countries pursue a Master or Bachelor of Laws degree. In some countries it is common or even required for students to earn another bachelor's degree at the same time. It is often followed by a series of advanced examinations, apprenticeships, and additional coursework at special government institutes. It is also planned to analyze a number of international legal documents related to the role of legal professionals in building a fair society in our country and increasing the international reputation of our country. Some countries, particularly industrialized ones, have a traditional preference for full-time law programs, while in developing countries, students often work full- or part-time to pay the tuition and fees of their part-time law programs. Law schools in developing countries share several common problems, such as an over reliance on practicing judges and lawyers who treat teaching as a part-time hobby (and a concomitant scarcity of full-time law

professors); incompetent faculty with questionable credentials; and textbooks that lag behind the current state of the law by two or three decades. The purpose of this scientific article is to determine the issues of international cooperation in the field of legal education of Uzbekistan, the importance of the experience of foreign countries in education, science and the training of personnel who can meet world standards, and the problems and solutions in this field. Today, many opportunities are being created for legal education, training of legal personnel who have a place in the labor market and are effective in the legal field. As one of them, it can be said that by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 453 of June 14, 2018, courses of re-training for legal specialization were organized at the center of professional training of legal personnel under international standards. These courses are a form of post-higher education training, which provides for the formation of sufficient knowledge and skills to work in professions and positions that require legal knowledge and knowledge of state bodies and organizations. All persons with higher education can submit documents and successfully pass entrance exams in the form of an interview and study for a retraining course. These courses only can be directed to have comprehension on personnel about their legal knowledge.

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